

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

INTRODUCING STATIC MALWARE ANALYSIS: TECHNIQUES AND TOOLS

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Abstract

Current state of malware phenomenon proceeds from rapid growths of technologies and IT industries. Malware mitigation and prevention steps involve implementation of reverse engineering, static and dynamic analyses. Dynamic malware analysis is a process of debugging a virus sample and inspecting its behavioristic pattern through monitoring violations and irregularities on a host machine. Static malware analysis is a set of techniques and tools to understand the nature and behavior of malicious software without executing it on the safe sandbox environment. This paper proposes an overview of signature-based detection of Trojan LOKIBOT Win32 malware on Windows Operation Systems, its process to spread infection to other hosts over the network and to address malignant data from victim machines to the target systems by maintaining espionage and stealing user credentials from monitored applications. Our focus on this research for Trojan LOKIBOT Win32 will be on vendor threat intelligence platforms and interactive sandbox environments.

Keywords: malware analysis, static malware analysis, antivirus, trojan horse, backdoor

Introduction.

Cybersecurity, in its own way, a relatively new and dynamic field, studies enormous domains of computer science, starting from network defense to cloud infrastructure risks. With the development of new generation technologies and devices over past decades, we are beginning to be vulnerable to common network attacks, advanced persistent threats, and computer viruses. Malware, short for Malicious Software, is a variety of a programmed software that is dedicated to infecting and harming relevant devices on the network segment. As any software itself, malware is grouped into several types: Trojans, a piece of executable program, which is disguised as a legitimate software to misinterpret users to upload and run it; spyware, a purpose of which an espionage; ransomware, a type of malware that blocks all user data on the endpoints and challenges users to pay a ransom to reverse back all documents. One of the most spread ransomware attacks “WannaCry” was in May 2017 [1], targeting endpoints of Microsoft Windows operating systems.

For strategies to mitigate and prevent malware spread, we apply certain designed analysis techniques and their respective tools: static analysis and dynamic analysis. These are two separate approaches used by cybersecurity specialists to examine and understand malware behavior. Static malware analysis involves analyzing a virus structure and pattern in a safe sandbox environment without executing a sample by using reverse engineering tools [2]. This approach aims to observe malware functionality and any potential vulnerabilities within a code to breach the chain of infection. Dynamic malware analysis conducts an execution of a malicious software in a controlled environment such as a virtual machine. It helps to survey existing IP addresses of attackers, registry keys, file path locations, and more. Both methods include a deep technique of

dissecting analysis – an advanced form of audit. Advanced static analysis [3,4] involves studying code deobfuscation, unpacking and decoding encrypted code to the readable format; function identification, determining modules, addresses of routines and variables of malware code; data flow analysis, identifying what vulnerable information the malware transmits to the destination address, behavioral analysis, to test potential damage impact; and signature creation, the main part of malware analysis, where we identify the unique signature for malicious sample to be recognized by antivirus software to prevent an analyzed malware from infecting other systems.

Methodology.

This paper proposes a survey on static malware analysis using VirusTotal for indicators of compromise, ANY.RUN an interactive sandbox intelligence, Hybrid analysis, Joe Sandbox, CAPE Sandbox and VMRAY malware analysis platform.

Materials and methods of research.

To analyze a malware sample, it was taken a malicious LOKIBOT Win32 executable package with 370.53 KB file size. Following indicators are introduced below on Table 1 and Table 2. Target machine for a given research is Intel 386 or later processors and compatible processors. A threat category is defined as trojan, with a label trojan.enna/llac. A sample has key imports: comdlg32.dll, version.dll, gdi32.dll, KERNEL32.DLL, user32.dll and the contacted IP address: 23.95.132.48 with ports 80 (HTTP), 445, (Active Directory), where network traffic from victim hosts is transmitting. This process comes with a malware connecting to the C&C server through application layer protocol and stealing user credentials and personal data from Web-browsers (Figure 1). Malicious attack starts to perform query registry by creating files or folders in the user directory, reading computer name, and machine GUID from registry.

Table 1

Indicators of Compromise (IOCs) of a LOKIBOT Win32	
Indicator of compromise	Description
SHA256 hash	8487ec9e7929cead8c5dcea98ee74b8e1735d53d5ca7993f93b37892fe3c6364
SHA1 hash	4927e54a99625475c2bc15c203b8e7e34c15afb5
MD5 hash	af60bffb6eb6ea0bda2e965bfacde58b4
File name	af60bffb6eb6ea0bda2e965bfacde58b4.exe
Signature	Loki
File type	exe
imphash	9c1c89f0b09f705763f261328623edb7
TrID	33.2% (.EXE) Win32 Executable (generic) (4505/5/1) 22.1% (.MZP) WinArchiver Mountable compressed Archive (3000/1) 14.9% (.EXE) OS/2 Executable (generic) (2029/13) 14.7% (.EXE) Generic Win/DOS Executable (2002/3) 14.7% (.EXE) DOS Executable Generic (2000/1)

Given sample is addressing user data to malicious links such as <http://alphastand.trade/alien/fre.php>, <http://kbfvzoboss.bid/alien/fre.php>, <http://23.95.132.48/>, <http://alphastand.top/alien/fre.php>, collecting information to fingerprint the system using regkey HKEY_LOCAL_MACHINE\SOFTWARE\Microsoft\Cryptography\MachineGuid. It executes a process of an injected code while unpacking a file, according to

arguments `f60bffb6eb6ea0bda2e9.exe(2680) -> af60bffb6eb6ea0bda2e9.exe(2868)` and harvests credentials from local FTP client software and information related to mail clients. Furthermore, a malicious sample installs itself for autorun at Windows startup by using `C:\Users\Admin\AppData\Roaming\Microsoft\Windows\Start Menu\Programs\Startup\file.vbs`. Analysis overview reports that most incoming traffics are from USA (Figure 2) with 3.56 KB total sent, 2.15 KB total received.

Table 2

Antivirus (AV) threat intelligence detection			
AV	Description	AV	Description
AhnLab-V3	Malware/Win.Win.R438175	Alibaba	Trojan:Win32/DelfInject.ali2000015
ALYac	Trojan.Agent.ENVA	Antiy-AVL	Trojan/Win32.Wacatac
Fortinet	W32/Injector.ELFW!tr	Avast	Win32:Malware-gen
Kaspersky	HEUR:Trojan.Win32.Llac.gen	McAfee-GW-Edition	Fareit-FUT!2E08588E943F
Microsoft	PWS:Win32/Fareit.VD!MTB	Palo Alto Networks	Generic.ml
Yandex	Trojan.GenAsa!1j77+Qms9mI	Sophos	Mal/Fareit-V
SecureAge	Malicious	Symantec	Infostealer.Lokibot!43
K7GW	Trojan (0051918e1)	Ikarus	Trojan.Win32.Injector

Since LOKIBOT malware acts as a stealer, its first function is to steal valid user credentials in order to spread malignant network traffic to other systems and hosts by successfully authorizing. However, this malware has a second addition as a stealthy trojan horse it can spy and monitor activities of a victim, slowly and

firmly take a full control of a target. As mentioned before, it stores password data from known application as: Putty, FTP Navigator, CheckMail, Postbox, EnPass, NexusFile, Orbitum, Maple, Foxmail, WinSCP, RoboForm, Outlook, Safari and more [5].

Figure 1. Process details of LOKIBOT Win32

Distribution of LOKIBOT malware is set through mail spams with suspicious files to download or through infected network to new network subnets.

Mitigation techniques require up-to-date antivirus signatures, patched operating systems, disabled file and

printer sharing services and ports, user permission restrictions, enabled two-factor authentication and basic cyber hygiene.

Figure 2. Network analysis of LOKIBOT Win32

Findings.

1. Static malware analysis on LOKIBOT Win32 backdoor is conducted with no execution of the malicious sample file using instruments on sandbox environments, resulting a full report of a global overview, network criteria, malware behavior, files, and indicators of compromise (IOCs).

2. Identified vulnerable paths and services for LOKIBOT Win32 backdoor on Windows operating systems to avoid incidents coming from malign activities in the future.

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